

Custom R Script for Simulation Analysis

```
r <- 0.2 # spousal correlation
h2eq <- 0.5 # (SNP-based) heritability in the equilibrium population
load("SupplementaryFigure.RData")
png("PGS_correlations_and_power.png",width=4000,height=2000,res=300)
op <- par(mfrow=c(1,2))
par(mar=c(5,5,3,2))
matplot(0:(nrow(R)-1),R,pch=19,xlab="Number of Generations of Assortative Mating",
        ylab="PGS correlations",cex.lab=1.2,axes=FALSE,ylim=c(0,0.12))
points(0:(nrow(R)-1),R[,"rSp"]/2,col=4,pch=19)
axis(1)
axis(2)
abline(h=r*h2eq*c(0.5,1),col=c("coral1","black"),lty=1:2)
legend(18,0.025,legend=c("Between Spouses",
                        "Odd/Even","Between Sibs (-0.5)",
                        "Between Spouses / 2"),box.lty=0,
       col=1:4,pch=19)
mtext("a",at=0,side=3,line=0,font=2,cex=1.5)

p <- function(rsp,a=0.05,Nsib,Nsp,Nunrel){
  t <- qchisq(p=a,df=1,ncp=0,lower.tail = FALSE)
  psp <- pchisq(q=t,df=1,ncp=Nsp*(rsp^2)/(1-rsp^2),lower.tail = FALSE)
  rOth <- rsp / 2
  psib <- pchisq(q=t,df=1,ncp=Nsib*(rOth^2)/(1-(0.5+rOth)^2),lower.tail = FALSE)
  pOE <- pchisq(q=t,df=1,ncp=Nunrel*(rOth^2)/(1-rOth^2),lower.tail = FALSE)
  pCb <- pchisq(q=t,df=1,
               ncp=Nsp*(rsp^2)/(1-rsp^2)
               + Nunrel*(rOth^2)/(1-rOth^2)
               + Nsib*(rOth^2)/(1-(0.5+rOth)^2),
               lower.tail = FALSE)
  pCb2 <- pchisq(q=t,df=1,
                ncp=Nsp*(rsp^2)/(1-rsp^2)
                + Nunrel*(rOth^2)/(1-rOth^2),
                lower.tail = FALSE)
  c(P_spouse=psp,P_OE=pOE,P_sib=psib,P_joint=pCb)
}
rs <- c(0.001,0.002,0.005,0.01,0.02,0.05,0.1)
powerMHQ <- do.call("rbind",lapply(rs, function(r) p(rsp=r,a=0.05,Nsib=17910,Nsp=38457,Nunrel=183353)))
powerPSY <- do.call("rbind",lapply(rs, function(r) p(rsp=r,a=0.05,Nsib=17910,Nsp=38457,Nunrel=271957)))

Cols <- c("dodgerblue","coral1","khaki3","goldenrod")
par(mar=c(5,5,3,2))
matplot(rs,powerMHQ,pch=19,type="l",log="x",col=Cols,lwd=2,
        xlab="Expected PGS correlation between spouses",
        ylab="Statistical power to detect AM in the UK Biobank (p<0.05)",axes=FALSE,
        main="",lty=1,cex.lab=1.2,ylim=c(0,1))
matpoints(rs,powerMHQ,pch=19,col=Cols)
axis(1,at=rs);axis(2)
```

```
legend(rs[1],1,title="Source of information",title.font = 2,  
      legend=c("Spouses pairs","Odd/Even Chromosomes","Siblings pairs","Meta-analysis"),  
      lty=1,col=Cols,lwd=2,cex=0.8,box.lty=0)  
abline(h=0.8,col="grey",lty=2)  
legend(0.015,0.2,legend=c("GWAS of MHQ","External GWAS"),pch=c(19,1),lty=1:2,box.lty=0)  
  
matlines(rs,powerPSY,lty=2,col=Cols)  
matpoints(rs,powerPSY,pch=1,col=Cols,cex=1.5)  
  
mtext("b",at=rs[1],side=3,line=0,font=2,cex=1.5)  
  
par(op)  
dev.off()
```

Custom R Script for calculating results expected from the cross-method meta-analysis

```
expected_AM_strength <- function(h2eq=0.8, # Pedigree heritability
                                h2snp=0.5, # SNP-based heritability
                                r=0.2,    # Spousal correlation
                                N=2.5e5,  # GWAS sample size
                                M=1e5){   # Number of causal variants (e.g., 1e4, 1e5)
  ## Derived parameters
  rho <- r * h2eq
  Q <- (N*h2eq/M)/(1-rho) # eq. 1.16 (Yengo et al. 2018, Suppl. Notes)
  Q_ <- 1/Q
  feq <- h2snp/h2eq
  D <- 4 * feq * rho * (1-rho * h2eq)/((1-rho)^3)
  f0 <- 0.5*(1-rho)*(sqrt(1+D)-1)/rho # eq. 1.20
  gamma <- 0.5*rho/(1-rho)
  ## Expected correlation
  thetaSNP <- ( rho * f0/(2-rho*(2-f0)) ) /
  ( 1 + Q_ * (1 + 0.5*(rho * f0)/(1-rho))^{-3} ) # eq. 1.17
  return(2 * thetaSNP)
}
```